

Allele: — CDC Landmark — CDC Stanley

Supplementary Fig. S1 Segregation of 2N^YS segment in DH progeny derived from CDC Stanley x CDC Landmark. The 2N^YS translocation (~33Mb) from *Aegilops ventricosa* is present in the short arm of chromosome 2A of CDC Stanmark but absent in CDC Landmark. Landmark470 and Stanley470 are high coverage WGS used in developing the respective reference genome. LandmarkDH and StanleyDH are used in developing StanleyLandmarkDH populations. Each panel shows the genomic position of a given chromosome in 1Mb bins on the physical map of the CDC Landmark reference genome in the x-axis with points showing the normalized number of reads mapping to the respective bin. The vertical axis shows both normalized read count (left) and chromosome dosage (right). The parental allele for individual SNP variants is shown on top for CDC Landmark (red) and CDC Stanley (blue) alleles.